

GREEN CONCRETE: AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract:

The Concrete which is made using the inorganic wastes is known as Green Concrete. It is quite eco-friendly and acts as a way to sustainable development of earth. This paper covers the feasibility of the usage of by-products such fly ash, pozzocrete, used foundry sand, etc. in concrete formation. The green concrete is formed by the partial replacement of cement and fine aggregates by its corresponding substitutes. This paper also deals with the effect on compressive strength of concrete when the cement is partially replaced by pozzocrete P60 as 30% by weight of cement and fine aggregates are replaced by used foundry sand as 10%, 25% and 50% by weight of cement. For this study, five sets of mixture proportions were prepared. The research was performed to study the technical benefits of partial replacing of cement and fine aggregates by their substitutes.

KEYWORDS

Sustainable Development, Pozzocrete P60, Fly Ash, Used Foundry Sand.

INTRODUCTION

Concrete is the most widely used man-made construction materials in the world that has various advantages such as available resources, easy operation, durability and steady mechanical properties. These characteristics make the concrete to be widely used in the construction of roads, bridges, hydraulic structures, multi-storey buildings, etc. Besides these advantages, there are some disadvantages such as consumption of raw material and high energy, environmental pollution, etc. which emphasize the question on the sustainability of concrete. In order to make the concrete as a sustainable material, the concept of “Green Concrete” was introduced.

Green Concrete is a concept of thinking environmental aspect with concrete by considering each and every element from manufacturing of raw material to their mix design, from structural design aspect to construction and serviceability aspect. It is very often and cheap to produce, because, for example, waste products acts as a partial substitute for cement, charges for the disposal of waste are avoided, energy consumption in production is lower, and durability is greater. The concrete should not be confused with its color.

As the natural resources are confined and the environment has to be protected from the waste products, therefore, these wastes can be used either to form new products or as admixtures. The Inorganic residuals like marble waste, stone dust can be considered as aggregate, the main body of the green concrete. Moreover, the fly ash can be used as the best alternative for cement along with micro silica in large amounts. The main objectives of using these wastes are to improve its durability eco-friendliness and cost effectiveness. This paper emphasizes the different efforts to improve the sustainability of concrete to make it suitable as a “Green Building” material.

Green Concrete: A Tool for Sustainable Construction

Sustainable Constructions are the constructions which are related to mitigate the prominent impact of environment and can sustain the constructions for their implications economically. The turn-out of Construction Industry has a major drawback on our ability to maintain a sustainable economy overall and has a major burden on our environment. Moreover, in order to achieve sustainable construction, we are supposed to bring some major changes in the existing theory of concrete technology.

Worldwide, Over 8-10 billion tones of concrete is produced every year. Such amount of concrete requires higher amounts of natural resources for aggregates and cement production. In addition, it is also estimated that manufacturing of one ton of Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) leads to evaluation of one ton of CO₂. CO₂ is considered as greenhouse gas which is major reason for global warming. Moreover, the manufacturing of OPC is very energy intensive. The disposal and demolition of various concrete structures leads to some other environmental burden. The construction debris constitutes large fraction our solid waste disposal problem. The concrete production uses nearly 1 trillion gallons of water each year throughout the world.

The above various reasons imply that the construction industry has become a victim of its own success and therefore is now faced with tremendous challenges to reduce the OPC’s impact on

the environment. In order to resolve the problem, we should use the concrete with very little amount of OPC as much as possible.

Suitability of Green Concrete in Construction Industry

The various factors which make the green concrete as suitable for construction industry are as follows:

- Lowers down the dead weight of structures
- Improves damping resistance to the building
- Lowers down the overall construction period by enhancing the speed of construction
- Reduces the emission of CO₂ in concrete industry by 30%.
- Enhances the waste product use by 20%.
- Good thermal and fire resistance.
- Higher compressive strength behavior of Green concrete with same water-cement as compared with conventional concrete.

Potential barrier to use Green Concrete

Despite of the above benefits of the green concrete, it has some potential barriers which lie in concrete properties, industry perception and cost effectiveness as explained below:

Concrete Properties: It has been observed that by using waste products as substitutes for cement could enhance certain kind of properties while undermines some others. For example, Yang et al. found that the use of crushed oyster shell improves the compressive strength but decreases the workability. Moreover, according to Siddique et al., the concrete which contains plastic aggregates has quite lower value of compressive and tensile strengths.

Industry Perception: Duxson pointed out that due to the product failure chances, the construction industry is quite conservative in nature. Hence, the use of waste materials acts as a barrier to use green concrete.

Cost Effectiveness: It is the only driving force for the construction industry to implement green concrete. In order to meet the required properties, reuse and recycling of wastes requires extra labor and energy input.

Aim of the Study

The present study is an attempt to find out the increase in compressive strength of concrete by using the substitutes such as pozzocrete P60, foundry sand of cement and fine aggregates respectively. It also aims to explore the suitability of green concrete in contrast to the existing construction material namely nominal concrete.

FRAMEWORK

To lower down the environmental impact of the concrete, the effective strategies are supposed to be implemented by the prudent use of various tools. This implementation requires the efforts from well focused research and development. A considerable theory exists on the different methods that can be used to improve the durability and mechanical properties. The emphasis will be done on the questions that how to prepare the green concrete by the effective use of various cement substitutes.

Tools and Strategies

In order to achieve the sustainable construction of green concrete, there are various tools and strategies such as:

- *Increased use of substitute cementitious material:* The industrial effluents such as fly ash, slag act as supplement cementitious material, which can be used as a substitute for OPC.
- *Reduced dependence on virgin material:* The dependence on the virgin material can be reduced by the effective use of recycled material.
- *Improved Mechanical Properties:* The effective use of recycled material leads to improve its mechanical properties such as compressive strength.
- *Reuse of Wash Water:* The recycling of wash water is readily achieved in practice and already required by law in some countries.
- *Improved durability:* By doubling the service life of our structures, we can cut in half the amount of material needed for their replacement.

Hypothesis

It is believed that cement concrete is the best construction material in terms of its compressive strength, durability, life, coefficient of thermal expansion. However, it lacks sustainability, cost effectiveness, self-weight. In addition, the use of large amount of cement leads to the emission of CO₂. This gas is one of the major reasons of green house effect.

Approach

The above mentioned tools and strategies clearly show that sustainable construction with green concrete can be done by various means. These various means are as follows:

Use of Geo-Polymer Concrete

The Geo-polymers when combined with materials such as fly ash, natural pozzolanas and ground granulated slag, produces the cement-less concrete. The Natural pozzolana exist in different grades such as P100, P60, P40, P30, etc. These materials are quite durable and strong. These are having high resistance power against acid and fire attack as compared with traditional OPC concretes. Geo-polymer concretes emit only 7% of CO₂ as that of traditional OPC concretes.

Partial Replacement of Cement

The lowering of OPC can be done by partial replacement of cement by various cementitious materials, such as ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBFS), fly ash, wood ash, limestone powder, etc. This method also reduces the heat of hydration which ultimately lowers down the thermal cracking risk. Moreover, it also acts as resistant to chemical attacks, chloride induced corrosion of reinforcing steel bars.

Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBFS): GGBFS is the best cementitious material. It is a by-product of iron and steel making in steam or water from a blast furnace. It is glassy and granular product followed by drying and grounding into fine powder. The amount of cement that can be replaced by GGBFS varies from 70%-80%. The production of this material is 25 million ton per year throughout the world, hence availability of this slag is not frequent as compared with the other replacement elements.

Fly Ash: The replacement level of cement by fly ash is nearly 80%. The use of fly ash in green concrete formation requires a chemical activator. Moreover, it lowers down the heat of hydration, mainly suitable for mass concrete applications. Its lower cost and abundant availability also plays an important factor to use it as a cement substitute.

Rice Husk Ash (RHA): Husk is a by-product of rice milling, which surrounds the paddy grain. During the milling of paddy grain, nearly 78% (w/w) is obtained as rice, broken rice and bran. Remaining 22% is received as husk. This husk acts as fuel in rice mills to form steam for parboiling process. This husk constitutes organic volatile matter (75%) and ash (25%). This ash, produced during firing process, is termed as Rice Husk Ash (RHA). The RHA constitutes nearly

85% - 90% of amorphous silica. It is considered as the most significant substitute cementitious material for concrete which reduces the emission of CO₂.

Silpozz: The RHA, when having particle size in range of 20-25 microns is termed as silpozz. These finer particles fill up the voids between cement and aggregates, followed by the reduction of cement amount in concrete mix. It enhances the compressive strength of the desired product by 10%-20%. The use of RHA reduces the heat of hydration by 30% and water penetration by 60%. It acts as highly resistant against chemical action, abrasion, corrosion in the reinforcement etc.

Use of Recycled Material

The various recycled material that can be used as cement substitute in green concrete are concrete debris, Cupolas slag, foundry sand, etc.

Concrete Debris: The Concrete debris can be considered as the component to be used as an aggregate in the new concrete production. During the demolition of the existing concrete structures, concrete debris is the largest fraction of concrete. By using the concrete debris, the conservation of natural resources can be done which ultimately reduces the use of virgin material.

Foundry Sand: The metal casting sand consists of high quality silica with uniform physical properties is known as Foundry Sand. It is mainly used as replacement for fine aggregates having upto 35% variations. The concrete formed by this sand fulfils all the standard requirements against IS codes for bulk density, absorption and bulk density.

Subjects:

The Green concrete can be produced by blending the different ratios of cement and fine aggregates with their substitutes. In this research work, the cement is replaced by Pozzocrete P60 and the fine aggregates are replaced by foundry sand. Pozzolana. During this research, the results were obtained for the concrete having mix proportion 1:1.52:3.25 in which partial replacement of cement is done by pozzocrete P60 as 30% (w/w) of cement and the fine aggregates are replaced by foundry sands as 10%, 25% and 50% (w/w) of fine aggregate. For this project, the five sets of mixtures were considered. First mix, A₀ was the nominal concrete without any pozzocrete or foundry sand. Second mix, C₀ was concrete that contained 30% pozzocrete P60 as a substitute for cement. The other mixes such as C₁, C₂, C₃ contained the mixture of 30% pozzocrete P60 and 10%, 25%, and 50% used foundry sand respectively.

Procedures:

To estimate the compressive strength of the green concrete, the research work is done under two heads i.e., Preparation of design mix material and compression testing of concrete.

Preparation of Design Mix Material

The various materials that are to be used for preparing the green concrete mix are cement, fine aggregate, foundry sand, pozzolane P60, water.

Cement: The cement used is Ambuja OPC 53 grade. To check the quality of cement, the various tests such as specific gravity, standard consistency, initial and final setting time, compressive strength at 28 days were conducted. The test results are as follows:

S.NO.	Physical Characteristics of Cement	Test Results	Requirement as per IS:8112-1989
1	Specific Gravity	3.12	3.10-3.15
2	Standard Consistency	32.50%	30-35
3	Initial Setting Time	37 minutes	30 minutes (minimum)
4	Final Setting Time	538 minutes	600 minutes (maximum)
5	Compressive Strength at 28 days	57.5 N/mm ²	53 N/mm ²

Table 1: Physical Characteristics of Cement

Water: Water is the only ingredient which is responsible for the chemical reactions to occur. To achieve the optimum desired strength, the quality of water should be maintained properly.

Fine Aggregates: The aggregates having particle size variation between 4.75mm to 150 microns are termed as fine aggregates. The river sand is mainly used as fine aggregates.

S.NO.	Characteristics of Fine Aggregate	Test Result
1	Fineness Modulus	3.08
2	Specific Gravity	2.78
3	Water Absorption	1.90%
4	Bulk Density	1.76 g/cc

Table 2: Characteristics of Fine Aggregates

Foundry Sand: Foundry sand consists of silica sand and coated with a thin film of burnt carbon, residual binder and dust. Residual binder constitutes bentonite, sea coal and resins. This sand can be used as partial replacement of either cement or fine aggregates. It can also act as a total replacement of fine aggregates.

Pozzocrete (P60): Pozzocrete, a highly efficient pozzolanic material, is obtained from the combustion of coal at electricity generating power station during the processing and testing of power station fly ash.

General Property	P60
Appearance	Finely divided dry powder
Specific Gravity	2.3
Colour	Light grey
Bulk Density	1.0 tonne per cubic metre
Particle Shape	Spherical
Particle Size	< 18% retained on 45 micron sieve

Table 3: General Properties of Pozzocrete (P60)

Design Mix Methodology

Concrete Composition: As per the IS: 10262-2009, cement concrete having mix proportions 1:1.52:3.25 was prepared and the same was used to prepare the specimens. The design mix proportion is shown below in the following tables:

	W (Lit.)	C (Kg/m3)	F.A. (Kg/m3)	C.A. (Kg/m3)
By Weight (Grams)	188.355	376.71	572.599	1224.307
By Volume (m3)	0.5	1	1.5	3

W= water, C = Cement, F.A. = Fine Aggregate, C.A. = Coarse Aggregate

Table 4: M20 Mix Design Proportion

S.NO.	Concrete Type	Concrete Description
1	A ₀	Standard
2	C ₀	30% P60
3	C ₁	30% P60 + 10% FS
4	C ₂	30% P60 + 25% FS
5	C ₃	30% P60 + 50% FS

Table 5: Concrete Replacement by Pozzocrete and Sand Replacement by Used Foundry Sand

Concrete Type	W/C Ratio	% Replacement		Design Mix Proportion for M20 Concrete				
		C	F.A.	C	F.A.	C.A	UFS	P60
A ₀	0.5	-	-	1	1.52	3.25	-	-
C ₀	0.5	30%	-	0.7	1.52	3.25	-	0.3
C ₁	0.5	30%	10%	0.7	1.37	3.25	0.15	0.3
C ₂	0.5	30%	25%	0.7	1.14	3.25	0.38	0.3
C ₃	0.5	30%	50%	0.7	0.76	3.25	0.76	0.3

W/C Ratio = Water Cement Ratio, UFS = Used Foundry Sand

Table 6: Design Mix Proportions for M20 Mix Concrete

Testing Methodology

From the design mix data, the green concrete was prepared followed by casting of three cube samples having mould size (150X150X150) mm for each 1:1.52:3.25. The water cement ratio was kept as 0.5. After 24 hours of casting, the specimens were de-moulded which is then followed by curing. These specimens were tested for compression strength after 7, 14 and 28

days one by one. In order to determine the compression testing of samples, the compression testing machine was used. The loading rate of the machine is 35 N/mm² per minute.

Presentation of Data

On the basis of compression test for the concrete specimen having mix proportion as 1:1.52:3.25, the comparative studies were made with partial replacement of cement and fine aggregates. The various results for compression testing of sample are given below:

Concrete Types	Compressive strength of Cement (N/mm ²)		
	7 days	14 days	28 days
A ₀	13.78	20.48	23.97
C ₀	19.27	27.98	31.36
C ₁	18.59	26.54	30.98
C ₂	20.63	29.29	32.18
C ₃	21.27	29.78	32.84

Table 7: Compressive Strength of Concrete for Design Mix M20 at 7, 14 and 28 days

Fig. 1: Concrete Types V/S Compressive Strength for M20 mix at 7 days, 14 days and 28 days

Conclusion and Scope of Future Research

To achieve the sustainable development on our planet, there are various means but Green Concrete is one of them. From the above research project, it is concluded that the use of pozzocrete P60 and foundry sand in the form of partial replacement of cement and fine aggregates is quite feasible for the strength. Considering the current scenario of green concrete material, the academic researchers would need to focus their studies on the impact on long-term properties of concrete structures such as creep, shrinkage, deflection, etc.

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